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Plant Growth Regulator: Polyamines used as for Regeneration and Growth of Chilli under Laboratory Condition

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ABSTRACT

Chilli is genus of flowering plants belongs to family Solanaceae. It is commonly used for nerve pain and other painful conditions. The role of polyamines has a great role in vitro techniques. Many scientists reported successive reports for growth and morphogenesis of polyamines. The objective of this study was to evaluate the beneficial impact of Chilli, nutritional aspects and role of polyamines on the germination, growth and development of plants. In Present study, the different concentration of polyamines was used to promote the morphogenesis, growth and development of Chilli plantlets from seed germination to attend the maturity of Plant. The seeds were spread over the blotting paper moistened with different concentrations of Polyamines (Spermine, Spermidine and Putrescine). The different concentration was 2µl, 4µl and 6µl per plate. The germinated seeds attained the plantlets after 15 days of inoculation, Later, hardening was done. Consequently, the plantlets attained the maturity having a lot of production of capsicum from each plant in Spermine (2µl) treatment, while seeds treated with putrescine and spermidine treated plants died. Putrescine is the central product of the common PA biosynthetic pathway. It contains two amino groups and is a synthetic precursor of SPD and SPM.

Keywords: Chilli, morphogenesis, polyamines, spermine, spermidine, putrescine

INTRODUCTION

Chilli is rich in minerals like potassium, iron, dietary fibres [12], carbohydrates, fats, Vitamin B6, vitamin C and sugar, which aids in the fight against oxidative stress and lowers the risk of chronic diseases. Chilli contains vitamin C, which helps the immune system fight infections (S). Several workers reported the impact of polyamines on several crops [3]. Polyamines are aliphatic compounds which are implicated in the regulation of abiotic and biotic stresses, development, and morphogenesis of plants. Many workers and scientists showed a fruitful impact on the growth of polyamines. In worldwide scenario, Chilli has a prominent role cultivation field to kitchen plate. The fruit of Chilli plants have a variety of names depending on place and type. Today, China, Turkey, Spain, Romania, Nigeria and Mexico produce most of the world's bell peppers. More peppers are being imported from Canada, Mexico, and Europe to meet their demand [10]. Its native is America and European countries. Polyamines have a remarkable role in the morphogenesis and growth of plants. *Capsicum* has a compact structure modified with a group of seeds. The Chilli

was introduced into India in two ways: first, by the Portuguese in South India and second by Arabian traders in North India. However, in Kumaon [17,18], it was first brought by Arabian traders who were indirectly assigned to trade capsicum with other products (Figure 1b). Chilli has risen from 7.1 pounds (3.2 kg) per capita in 1992 to 8.3 pounds (3.8 kg) per capita in 2002 [2]. Polyamines provide a basic role for future research on the mechanism of action of PAs in plant growth and development. PAs promote plant growth and development in production. Culinary curries, Vegetable and chicken tikkas, Starter and prickles. It has been used in many traditional medicines such heart diseases, neurological disorders, antibacterial and anticancer [15,16]. It is rich in a variety of phytochemicals like vitamins, anthocyanins, flavonoids, phenolic acid, capsaicinoids and carotenoids [13]. The more piquant varieties are commonly called chili peppers, or simply chilies. in North America and South Africa, sweet pepper or simply pepper in the United Kingdom and Ireland, but typically called capsicum in Australia, India, Malaysia, New Zealand and Singapore (Figure 1a).[4,11]

Fig. 1: Map showing worldwide production of Chilli.
(Source: <https://www.google.com/search?q=capsicum+PRODUCTION>)

Chilies are known to protect against gastrointestinal ailments including dyspepsia, loss of appetite, gastroesophageal reflux disease and gastric ulcer due to the several mechanisms such as reducing the food transition time through the gastrointestinal tract and anti-*Helico pylori* effects. Several studies reported that capsicum has a good phenomenon to control obesity. The cultivars of *Capsicum annum* is small shrubs with many branches and thin stems. The shrub has oval glossy leaves, sometimes growing to 6.5cm in length. They are generally green, The leaves are dark purple or black as the plant ages. *Capsicum annum* are annual or biennial herbaceous plants. The life cycle has four stages (seedling, vegetation, flowering, and fruiting). The different shapes of flowers and fruits produced on bell shaped flowers coming in a range of colors including purple, white, and green. The fruits of this species comes in various shapes (berry shape to bell pepper shape), and colors including red, yellow, green, and black. The daily intake of *Capsicum* in your diet may reduce the obesity and lipid formation capacity. Many literature surveys showed the use of capsicum fruits as a food additive in every recipes. In traditional medicine, Red pepper is generally feed to atonic dyspepsia and flatulence affected patient due to increasing the motility in the gastric antrum, duodenum, proximal jejunum and colon. It can also increase parietal, pepsin, and bile acid secretions.

TYPES OF CHILLI

There are different types of pigmented capsicum:

- Red
- Yellow
- Green
- Orange

In most of the kitchen and restaurant, *Capsicum* is commonly used for **culinary**

purposes. They can be bought in various colors and sizes, fresh or in powder used for sweet taste and a crunchy texture. Some of them are given below:

- **Cooked:** For prolonged preservation, *Capsicum* fried and prepared as chutneys.
- **Powder.** Red *Capsicum* is dried and ground into a powder called paprika, which provides as anti-inflammatory agent.
- **Pickled.** *Capsicum* can be pickled in a water and vinegar solution and eaten on sandwiches, in salads, and can be stored for prolong times.
- **Raw.** *Capsicum* contains more nutrients when eaten raw in salads, cold soups, or as a garnish for main dishes.

Systematic Classification

- Kingdom: Plantae
- Clade: Angiosperm
- Order: Solanales
- Genus: *Capsicum*

HERBAL REMEDIES & SUPPLEMENTS

- **Essential oil:** The oil extracted from sweet capsicum has high contents of carotenoids which promote healthy skin, hair, and nails.
- **Ointment.** Green and red *Capsicum* contain high levels of beta-carotene and can be used to soothe skin rashes and dryness and used to cure joint inflammation.
- **Capsules:** *Capsicum* contains a high contents of vitamins and minerals, they are to prepare capsules.

HEALTH BENEFITS OF CHILLI [13]

Improve Eye Health

Chilli has high content of carotene like carotenoids, lutein and zeaxanthin. Carotenoids protect the retina and promote

eye health. Besides, due to presence of vitamin c, it reduces cataract.

Role in Osteoporosis

For growth and development of healthy bones, magnesium is required. Chilli has high content of Magnesium. Magnesium helps in the formation of bone cartilage. Capsicum also contains a good source of vitamin K and Calcium which strengthen bones and reduces the osteoporosis.

Act as Antianaemia

Anaemia is caused due to iron deficiency. When the iron level decreases in our body, it leads to the positive impact of iron deficiency. Capsicum contains a high amount of vitamin C and iron. This combination increases the effective absorption of iron and prevents anaemia.

Act as Antianxiety

Chilli is a good source of vitamins and minerals that benefit the nervous system and reduces anxiety. It also helps with panic attacks. On the other hand, Capsicum also contains a compound called capsaicin, which acts as an endorphin. These compounds reduce the risk of depression and stress.

Role as Anticancer Agent

Chilli plays an important role as anticancer agent. It is rich in antioxidants [14], seems to reduce the risk of bladder, pancreas, cervix and prostate cancer.

Improves Body Metabolism

Chilli contains a good amount of carbohydrates and dietary fibre. It helps regulate the digestion process and also provides relief from constipation. Besides, it also promotes weight loss.

Benefits for Skin

Chilli is rich in vitamin C, which benefits our skin. Regular consumption of capsicum gives a natural glow to the skin.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The seeds of *Capsicum annum* were collected from nearby KVK, Sirohi Rajasthan. The seeds were washed with Sodium hypochlorite Solution. After 2minutes, the seeds were washed with distilled water for a second and later use for further experiment.

Seed Distribution and Polyamines in Petri plate

The concentration includes 2µl, 4µl and 6µl. The polyamines supplemented media with Distilled water were autoclaved before using. Triplicates were made along with control petri plate. In each petri plate, 12 seeds were inoculated. The observation was made after 72 hours of inoculation. The temperature was maintained at 25 ± 2 °C. Now the seeds were spread over the filter paper moistened with distilled water having different concentration of polyamines.

Nutritional Analysis of Chilli was done by Gopalam et al. 1996.[9]

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Polyamines are key players in modulating cell division and its rate. This indicates the importance of PAs in plant development and germination which could be the reason behind performance of Pas [5,6,7]. Polyamines are ubiquitous and aliphatic compound. They have a significant impact on morphogenesis and growth of both lower and higher plants. Since many years ago, polyamines have been used as a growth promoting substance for tissue culture [1]. Improvement in growth attributes might be the result of increased cell division within the apical meristem, causing augmented seedling growth [5]. The treatment of capsicum seeds in polyamines shown a rapid germination in present study. Several workers reported that seedling growth has also been improved by the seed priming with all PAs which in turn indicates invigorated

seedling vigor. These results could be clearly observed through higher root and shoot length, seedling fresh and dry weights. In most of the crops, in present study, approximately, 12 seeds were germinated in *in vitro* conditions with the application of different concentration (2 μ l, 6 μ l and 8 μ l) of Polyamines. When seeds attained maturity condition, they transferred to pots having analyzed soil. The environmental parameters were also recorded. Inside laboratory, the temperature was maintained nearly 25°C, however *in vivo* condition, the temperature

ranges up to 28°C. Sedimentation was observed firstly after 72 hour of inoculation. Hardening plays an important role for pre-stage growth of baby plant [8]. After hardening, A vigorous growth of root, shoot and leaves were observed (Present Study). In spermine supplemented distilled water culture plant showed best and healthier growth of fruitful plant in comparison to putrescine and spermidine treated plant. The maximum growth of plant inside the Petri dish measures 4cm in length (Figure 3).

Fig. 2(a): Seeds germinated on the polyamines (Spermine) moistened blotting paper, **2(b):** Baby Plant of Capsicum in Tray having soil, **2(c):** Farmer harvested Capsicum, **2(d):** Putrescine treated seed, **2(e):** Several pigmented Capsicum.

Later, the young plants transferred to tray containing soil for hardening (Figure 3). During this study, all the PAs stimulated seed germination and seedling growth compared to control, but Put was found more effective. The spraying of pesticides was done at regular intervals of time (Figure 3). The nature of the fruit was similar as natural growing fruit. If we come to nutritional analysis, the nutritional content also seems to be high in spermine supplemented green capsicum plant (Figure 2a). On the other hand, putrescine and spermidine supplemented seed seem to germinate but very slow growth (Figure 2d) Putrescine at lower concentrations was found better as compared to other PAs, which confirms the results of Farooq et al. (2008) but contrast to the findings of Farooq et al. (2007) and Farooq et al. (2011). The graphical representation shows very sharp margin of nutritional

content in Green Capsicum than Red and Yellow Capsicum (Figure 2a to 2e).[5,6,7] Water content has significant impact in green capsicum. It was found that Green Capsicum has highest nutritional contents than Red and Yellow Capsicum (Figure 2b & 2c). The order of nutritional Contents was followed as Green Capsicum>Red Capsicum>Yellow Capsicum as shown in Fig 3-5 below. However, the harvested pigmented capsicum was shown in Figure 2a. In Figure 2c and 2d, spermine supplemented mature healthy plants seemed to grow rapidly, while other plants treated with putrescine and spermidine died after 7 days of hardening. The root seemed to have a vigorous growth measuring 3.5cm in length, white pale yellow in colour. However, shoots was also reported to grow rapidly in spermine (6µl) treatment plant.

Fig. 3: Showing the nutritional content of Green Chili.

Fig. 4: Showing the nutritional content of Red Chilli.

Fig. 5: Showing the nutritional content of Yellow Chilli

CONCLUSION

The nutritional components of Chilli have shown great beneficial attributes so it should be cultivated easily and best employment opportunity to earn the livelihood. Polyamines like Putrescine and Spermidine have shown very rare growth of seeds and plants even after one month. Thus, polyamines seem to be good candidates in present experiments for early germination of seeds and plants.

Conflict of Interest

The author has no conflict of interest.

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